

1 **Effect of inbreeding on sheep semen traits.** The most important observed consequence of
2 inbreeding is the decrease of performance and fitness of the animals. This phenomenon is
3 known as inbreeding depression. Here, we estimate inbreeding depression for semen traits
4 while at the same time comparing different methods to estimate inbreeding coefficients. In
5 sheep, inbreeding from pedigree tends to be underestimated due to missing pedigrees, and
6 inbreeding from genomic information does not involve all animals because many of them are
7 not genotyped. Some of these methods are more appropriate to handle missing pedigree and
8 to include genotyped and non-genotyped animals in the analysis.

9

10 **Running head:** Inbreeding depression in sheep semen traits

11

12 **Genomic and pedigree estimation of inbreeding depression for semen traits in Basco-**
13 **Béarnaise dairy sheep breed**

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24

ABSTRACT

25 The understanding of inbreeding depression, the reduction in fitness and performance in the
26 offspring of matings of close relatives, is essential in animal breeding. The goal of this study
27 was to estimate inbreeding depression for three semen traits (volume, concentration and
28 motility score) while at the same time comparing different methods to estimate inbreeding
29 coefficients in Basco-Béarnaise breed. Data comprised 16,196 (or 15,071) phenotypic records
30 from 620 rams (of which 533 rams with genotype of 36,464 SNPs). There were 8,266
31 animals in the pedigree composed of the 620 rams and their ancestors.

32 Inbreeding coefficients were estimated using genomic and pedigree-based information.

33 Genomic inbreeding coefficients were estimated from individual SNP and using segments of
34 homozygous SNP (runs of homozygosity, ROH). Short ROHs are of old origin whereas long
35 ROHs are due to recent inbreeding. Considering that the equivalent number of generations in
36 Basco-Béarnaise was 6, inbreeding coefficients for ROH (1) with a length greater than 4 Mb
37 refers to all (recent + old) inbreeding, (2) with a length greater than 17 Mb corresponds to
38 recent inbreeding and (3) the difference between (1) and (2) indicates old inbreeding.

39 Pedigree-based inbreeding coefficients were also estimated classically, or accounting for non-
40 zero relationships for unknown parents, or including metafounder relationships (estimated
41 using markers) to account for missing pedigree information. Finally, inbreeding coefficients
42 combining genotyped and non-genotyped animal information were computed from matrix H
43 of Single-Step approach including also metafounders.

44 Inbreeding depression was estimated differently depending on the approach used to compute
45 inbreeding coefficients. These eight estimators of inbreeding coefficients were included as
46 covariates in different animal models. No inbreeding depression was detected for sperm
47 volume or sperm concentration. Inbreeding depression was significant for the motility of
48 spermatozoa. The effect of old inbreeding on motility was null whereas it was negative for

49 recent inbreeding, evidencing the existence of purging by selection of deleterious recessive
50 alleles affecting motility. A 10% increase in inbreeding would result in a reduction in the mean
51 motility ranging between 0.09 – 0.22 points in the score (from 0 to 5). Motility is unfavourably
52 impacted by increasing of recent inbreeding but the impact is very small.

53

54 **Key words:** inbreeding depression, ROH, metafounders, semen traits, Basco-Béarnaise
55 sheep.

56

INTRODUCTION

57

58 Inbreeding depression is the reduction, due to inbreeding, of the mean phenotypic value
59 shown by traits connected with fitness. The literature shows that inbreeding depression may
60 affect any trait under selection (Pryce et al., 2014; Ferenčaković et al., 2017). The genetic
61 basis of inbreeding depression remains unclear. There are currently two alternative
62 hypotheses to explain inbreeding depression, the partial dominance and the overdominance
63 hypotheses (Charlesworth & Willis, 2009). The ‘dominance hypothesis’ argues that
64 inbreeding depression is due to the presence of recessive alleles in populations. These alleles
65 present at low frequencies in populations can contribute to inbreeding depression because
66 homozygotes are rare except after inbreeding. Other hypothesis is the loss of the advantage
67 from alleles with heterozygous superiority (‘overdominance hypothesis’) due to the increase
68 of homozygosity. Recent results suggest that the role of partial dominance hypothesis is
69 major in comparison to the overdominance hypothesis (Leroy, 2014; Curik et al., 2017).

70

71 Inbreeding depression can be estimated from the regression of the phenotype on inbreeding
72 coefficients. Classically, the inbreeding coefficient is defined as the probability that both
73 alleles at any locus within an individual are identical by descent (IBD), and has been
74 computed from pedigree information. However, pedigree information is incomplete, it
75 contains errors and inbreeding can be underestimated. Also, it assumes an infinitesimal model
76 with unrelated loci. Different methods are available to compute inbreeding coefficients for
77 populations with missing pedigrees (VanRaden, 1992; Aguilar and Misztal, 2008). The
78 availability of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) allows to estimate genomic inbreeding
79 coefficients from individual SNP or from segments of homozygous SNP (runs of
80 homozygosity, ROH). These genomic inbreeding coefficients are expected to be more
81 accurate because they reflect that inheritance is passed on in chromosomes. Genomic

82 inbreeding coefficient estimates obtained from individual SNP refer to the proportion of
83 homozygous genotypes (Silió et al., 2013) and do not use information from contiguous
84 markers. Genomic inbreeding coefficient estimates based on ROH provides a better measure
85 of inbreeding because it contemplates the joint occurrence of inbreeding in neighboring
86 markers, and the length of ROH can give insight into the age of inbreeding allowing to
87 distinguish between recent and old inbreeding (Curik et al., 2017). Old inbreeding is typically
88 less relevant because it is expected to be purged from deleterious load, whereas recent
89 inbreeding is not.

90

91 Two obstacles to compute inbreeding in dairy sheep are the lack of pedigree recording and
92 the lack of genotyping. Pedigree is missing as the sire is (usually) not recorded except for
93 Artificial Insemination (AI) offspring. VanRaden (1992) proposed a method to estimate
94 inbreeding coefficients compensating for missing pedigrees. Essentially the method consists
95 in assigning relationships to pools of missing parents. Legarra et al. (2015) proposed a similar
96 idea, called metafounders, where these relationships were obtained based on markers of
97 descendants of these pools.

98

99 Genomic methods (*e.g.* ROH) are powerful but require that all animals have been genotyped.
100 This is rarely the case in sheep populations. Single-Step methods (Aguilar et al., 2010;
101 Christensen and Lund, 2010), that project genomic relationships to all non-genotyped
102 members of the pedigree, palliate such problems and permits to estimate single SNP-based
103 genomic inbreeding coefficients (but not ROH) for all animals (genotyped and ungenotyped).
104 Recently, different methods to efficiently compute inbreeding coefficients were proposed
105 (Legarra et al., 2020) and they include the use of metafounders (Legarra et al., 2015; Garcia-
106 Baccino et al., 2017) as an option for modeling missing pedigree.

107

108 In dairy sheep, AI with fresh semen is used with reproductive and genetic purposes. AI
109 success depends on male fertility and sperm quality among other factors. In dairy cattle,
110 several studies concluded that sperm quality is susceptible to inbreeding depression (*e.g.*
111 Maximini et al., 2011; Ferenčaković et al., 2017). However, to date, the effect of inbreeding
112 on semen traits has not been quantified in dairy sheep data. AI rams play a major role in
113 selection schemes and monitoring of inbreeding depression on semen traits is of interest.

114

115 The goal of this study is to estimate inbreeding depression for semen traits (sperm volume,
116 sperm concentration and motility) in Basco-Béarnaise rams while at the same time comparing
117 different methods to estimate inbreeding coefficients. Inbreeding coefficients were computed
118 based on genomic and pedigree information and were used as covariate in an animal model.

119

120

121

MATERIALS AND METHODS

122 Data for this study were extracted of the French National dairy sheep database for Basco-
123 Béarnaise breed. Animal Care and Use Committee approval was not necessary for this study
124 because the data were obtained from an existing database.

125

Phenotypic and genomic data

127 Due to the use of fresh semen, a large population of rams is held in AI center (Centre
128 Départemental de l'Élevage Ovin), in Ordiarp, Pyrénées Atlantiques, France). Semen
129 production and quality data has been routinely collected for rams born between 1997 and
130 2015. Sperm volume was evaluated directly by reading the collection tube (mL). Sperm
131 concentration was determined by spectrophotometer ($\times 10^6$ spermatozoa / mL). Motility score

132 was evaluated by a technician on a scale from 0 (no motion) to 5 (numerous, rapid and
133 vigorous waves) under the microscope. Data comprised 16,196 phenotypic records from 620
134 rams born between 1997 and 2015. Summaries of the whole data for different semen traits are
135 presented in Table 1.

136

137 *Table 1*

138

139 From the 620 rams with records, genotyped animals are a subset of 533 rams. These rams
140 were genotyped using the OvineSNP50 Bead-Chip (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA). The
141 distribution of rams and status (genotyped or not) across year of birth is shown in Figure 1.
142 After quality control using default parameters by preGSf90 (Aguilar et al., 2014) (Hardy-
143 Weinberg equilibrium, minor allele frequency, SNP call rate and animal call rate), 36,464
144 autosomal SNP remained and were used to build genomic relationship matrices.
145 Pedigree was extracted from the national database. There were 8,266 animals in the pedigree
146 composed of the 620 rams and their ancestors. In the complete pedigree, 14% and 10% of the
147 animals have one or two unknown parents, respectively.

148

149 *Figure 1*

150

151 ***Genomic inbreeding estimation***

152 Inbreeding coefficient based on individual SNP (F_{SNP}) was defined as the proportion of
153 homozygous SNP in each animal (Silió et al., 2013). Thus, for the animal i (F_{SNP_i}), it was
154 calculated for the whole genome as $F_{SNP_i} = \frac{N_{AA} + N_{aa}}{N_{AA} + N_{Aa} + N_{aa}}$ where N_{AA} , N_{Aa} and N_{aa} refers to
155 the number of SNP that are classified as AA , Aa and aa , respectively.

156

157 The inbreeding coefficient based on ROH (F_{ROH}) is the proportion of the genome that is in
 158 ROH. For animal i , F_{ROH_i} is calculated as $F_{ROH_i} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{ROH_i}} l_{ROH_{ik}}}{l_g}$ where n_{ROH_i} represents the
 159 total number of ROH in animal i , $l_{ROH_{ik}}$ is the length of the k^{th} ROH in animal i in base pairs,
 160 and l_g is the length of the genome in base pairs.

161

162 Several criteria exist for identifying a ROH, which involve the homozygous or heterozygous
 163 state of the SNP and its map position. The criteria and the values assessed in this study were:
 164 (1) the minimum length that constituted a ROH was 4 Mb, (2) 30 as the minimum number of
 165 SNP, (3) a minimum density of 1 SNP / 100 kb, (4) 1 Mb as the maximum distance allowed
 166 between two consecutive homozygous SNP, (5) maximum of two missing genotypes, and (6)
 167 only one heterozygous genotype was allowed. Recently, Rodriguez-Ramilo et al. (2019)
 168 showed that this set of values is appropriate for the Basco-Béarnaise breed.

169

170 Runs of homozygosity due to recent inbreeding are expected to be longer than ROH due to
 171 old inbreeding (repeated meiosis splits homozygous segments) (McQuillan et al., 2008). To
 172 determine the number of generations from a common ancestor (gcA), and consequently, to
 173 differentiate recent from old inbreeding, the following formula was used (Curik et al., 2014):

$$174 \quad E(L_{IBD-H}|gcA) = 100/(2gcA)$$

175 where $E(L_{IBD-H}|gcA)$ is the expected length of an IBD haplotype. This means that ROH
 176 with a minimum length of 4 Mb come from a common ancestor occurring 12.5 generations
 177 ago. Accordingly, ROH with a minimum length of 17 Mb come from a common ancestor
 178 occurring 3 generations ago. Taking into account that the equivalent number of generations in
 179 Basco-Béarnaise was estimated as six (Rodriguez-Ramilo et al., 2019), $F_{ROH>4Mb}$ refers to all
 180 inbreeding, $F_{ROH>17Mb}$ to recent inbreeding, and $F_{ROH\ 4-17Mb} = F_{ROH>4Mb} - F_{ROH>17Mb}$

181 refers to old inbreeding. In the next sections, $F_{ROH>4Mb}$, $F_{ROH\ 4-17Mb}$ and $F_{ROH>17Mb}$ are
182 called $F_{ROH_{Total}}$, $F_{ROH_{Old}}$ and $F_{ROH_{Recent}}$, respectively. Inbreeding coefficient estimates based
183 on ROH were calculated for the whole genome.

184

185 ***Pedigree inbreeding estimation***

186 Pedigree-based inbreeding coefficients were estimated using four methods. The first method
187 (F_{PED}) used the traditional pedigree-based inbreeding. The second method ($F_{PED_{non-zero}}$) used
188 pedigree-based inbreeding but accounting for non-zero relationships for unknown parents
189 (VanRaden, 1992; Aguilar and Misztal, 2008). In this approach, animals with missing parents
190 were assumed to have inbreeding coefficients equal to the mean of the inbreeding coefficients
191 for animals with known parents born during the same year. The third method used the
192 metafounder relationships in pedigree-based inbreeding ($F_{PED_{MF}}$), i.e. it compensates for
193 missing pedigree assigning non-zero relationships to metafounders. Metafounders are pseudo-
194 animals that represent relationship across and within base populations. For instance, unknown
195 parents of an animal born in 2000 are likely offspring of animals born in 1996, but this
196 relationship is lost if metafounders are not used. We used five metafounders, as described
197 below. The fourth method calculates inbreeding from a combined relationship matrix (\mathbf{H}) using
198 pedigree and genotypes with metafounder relationships ($F_{H_{MF}}$). The diagonal element of
199 matrix \mathbf{H} minus 1 gives an estimate of the inbreeding coefficient. For genotyped animals, it
200 can be shown that $2F_{SNP} = 1 + F_{H_{MF}}$ (Garcia-Baccino et al., 2017).

201

202 In this study, five metafounders were defined, as a function of birth year of animals with
203 unknown parent: 1974-1980, 1980-1988, 1988-1994, 1994-2000, > 2000. Ancestral
204 relationships or relatedness for base animals (matrix $\mathbf{\Gamma}$), were estimated from pedigree and

205 genotypes of the 533 genotyped rams using generalized least squares (Garcia-Baccino et al.,
206 2017).

207

208 *Evaluation models*

209 Phenotypes were analysed using separate single-trait mixed models (multiple-trait analyses
210 gave similar results). The combined effect of year-season of collection, the daily variation
211 (AM/PM), the age at collection (years) and the interval from previous collection (days, from
212 1 to 8) were included as fixed effects. The model also included a random permanent effect for
213 each ram. For a single trait, the linear model can be written as:

$$214 \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{F}b + \mathbf{Z}_u\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{Z}_{pe}\mathbf{pe} + \mathbf{e}$$

215 where \mathbf{y} is the vector of phenotypic records (volume, concentration, and motility), $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the
216 vector of fixed effects, \mathbf{u} is the vector of additive genetic effects, \mathbf{pe} is the vector of
217 permanent environmental effects ($Var(\mathbf{pe}) = \mathbf{I}\sigma_{pe}^2$), \mathbf{e} is a residual vector ($Var(\mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^2$),
218 and \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Z} are design matrices relating records to fixed and random effects, respectively.

219 The term $\mathbf{F}b$ models the inbreeding depression, where b is the inbreeding depression
220 parameter per unit of inbreeding, and the covariate \mathbf{F} is the vector of inbreeding coefficients.
221 Eight different inbreeding coefficients were tested: genomic (\mathbf{F}_{SNP} , $\mathbf{F}_{ROH_{Total}}$, $\mathbf{F}_{ROH_{Old}}$ and
222 $\mathbf{F}_{ROH_{Recent}}$) and pedigree-based (\mathbf{F}_{PED} , $\mathbf{F}_{PED_{non-zero}}$, $\mathbf{F}_{PED_{MF}}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{H_{MF}}$). Accordingly, the
223 use of these eight inbreeding coefficients defined eight models: SNP, ROH_{Total}, ROH_{Old},
224 ROH_{Recent}, PED, PED_{non-zero}, PED_{MF} and H_{MF}, respectively. In addition, the different models
225 differ in the number of records used and in the relationship matrices used for $Var(\mathbf{u})$ in the
226 linear model.

227 The first four (genomic) models (SNP, ROH_{Total}, ROH_{Old}, ROH_{Recent}) only included 533
228 genotyped rams with 15,071 records, as the other rams do not have genotype. In this case,

229 $Var(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{G}\sigma_u^2$, where \mathbf{G} is VanRaden (2008) genomic relationship matrix, and a GBLUP
230 was used.

231 The other four models (PED, PED_{non-zero}, PED_{MF} and H_{MF}) included the 16,196 records from
232 the 620 rams. In the two models PED and PED_{non-zero}, $Var(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{A}\sigma_u^2$, the classical
233 numerator relationship matrix. In the PED_{MF} model, $Var(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{A}^F\sigma_u^2$, pedigree-based
234 relationship matrix but including metafounders. The last model H_{MF} was single-step GBLUP
235 with metafounder relationships ($Var(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{H}^F\sigma_a^2$) (Legarra et al., 2015).

236

237 Variance components for semen traits were estimated from phenotypes and pedigree
238 information by REML once in model PED and assumed known for the remaining models.
239 Programs of the BLUPF90 family (Misztal et al., 2002) were used for the analyses and are
240 available at <http://nce.ads.uga.edu/wiki/doku.php>.

241

242

243 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

244 Heritability estimates for sperm volume, sperm concentration and motility were 0.09 ± 0.02 ,
245 0.07 ± 0.02 and 0.05 ± 0.02 , respectively. These heritability values agree with values reported
246 in the literature for other sheep breeds (0.11 for volume (Rege et al., 2000), 0.06 for
247 concentration (Duval et al., 1995) and 0.04 for motility (David et al., 2007)).

248

249 Mean inbreeding coefficients across individuals for each method are shown in Table 2. The
250 highest values of inbreeding among F_{ROH} averages correspond to $F_{ROH_{Total}}$. It was expected
251 because it includes all the fragments having a length higher than 4 Mb (Ferenčaković et al.,
252 2017). The mean F_{SNP} and $F_{ROH_{Total}}$ were 0.61 and 0.05, respectively. Note that individual

253 SNP inbreeding is the combination of IBD and IBS; while F_{ROH} represents only the IBD
 254 fraction (Curik et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015; Peripolli et al., 2017). As expected, $F_{ROHTotal}$
 255 is close to pedigree-based inbreeding coefficients, F_{PED} and $F_{PED_{non-zero}}$. Among pedigree-
 256 based coefficients, the higher values were for methods that include metafounder
 257 relationships, $F_{PED_{MF}}$ and $F_{H_{MF}}$. Inbreeding increases when considering metafounders (0.03
 258 vs. 0.22) (Legarra et al., 2015). However, inbreeding depression estimates are not concerned,
 259 because adding a constant to a covariate does not change the regression. The rate of increase
 260 of inbreeding, calculated as the regression of pedigree inbreeding on birth year was 0.08% by
 261 year.

262 *Table 2*

263
 264 The correlations between the inbreeding coefficients for the 533 genotyped animals are
 265 shown in Figure 2. As expected, high correlation was obtained between F_{SNP} and $F_{ROHTotal}$
 266 (0.86), because short ROH contain small fragments of continuous SNP. The correlation
 267 varied from 0.91 to 0.97 between pedigree-based inbreeding coefficients: F_{PED} , $F_{PED_{non-zero}}$
 268 and $F_{PED_{MF}}$. The higher correlation was between F_{SNP} and $F_{H_{MF}}$ (1.00) as the corresponding
 269 block of \mathbf{H}^T is proportional to an IBS relationship \mathbf{G} -matrix (Garcia-Baccino et al., 2017).
 270 The lower correlation was between $F_{ROH_{Old}}$ and $F_{ROH_{Recent}}$ (0.19). The reason is that they
 271 reflect different age of inbreeding. In recent inbreeding, recombination and mutation did not
 272 fragment yet the homozygous segments. Ignoring F_{SNP} , inbreeding coefficients obtained from
 273 H matrix including metafounder relationships ($F_{H_{MF}}$) were mainly correlated with $\mathbf{F}_{ROHTotal}$
 274 (0.86) and in second and third place with old, $F_{ROH_{Old}}$ (0.68) and recent inbreeding,
 275 $F_{ROH_{Recent}}$ (0.65), respectively.

276

277

Figure 2

278

279 Estimates of inbreeding depression for the three evaluated traits are shown in Table 3. No
280 inbreeding depression was detected for sperm volume and sperm concentration. Inbreeding
281 depression for motility was significantly different of zero ($p < 0.05$) in SNP, ROH_{Total},
282 ROH_{Recent}, PED_{MF} and H_{MF} (in Table 3). The reduction in the mean motility score ranged
283 between 0.9% – 2.2% for a 100% of inbreeding. This means that a 10% of increase in
284 inbreeding would result in a reduction of the motility mean of around 0.1 points in the scale
285 (from 0 to 5) and a slight deterioration in semen quality. However, an inbreeding depression
286 of 0.1 points in motility is small and does not have a sensible economic impact for breeders.

287

288

Table 3

289

290 No inbreeding depression was detected for motility with ROH_{Old} which refers to old
291 inbreeding. A purging effect of deleterious alleles in old generations could explain this result
292 (Mc Parland et al., 2009). This purging effect has been identified in plants and animals
293 (Leroy, 2014). Purge is to occur if selection for a specific trait is strong relative to drift
294 leading to the elimination of the deleterious alleles. The difference between the old
295 inbreeding depression and the new one may be due to the fact that old deleterious alleles are
296 likely to have been purged in comparison to the new ones.

297

298 In sheep, complete pedigrees are difficult to obtain due to the use of natural mating.
299 Metafounders help with missing pedigree information, because ancestral relationships are
300 invariable to depth and completeness of the pedigree. Missing parents were modeled as
301 animals coming from base populations that might be related and inbred. Due to purge, only

302 “recent” inbreeding seems to cause inbreeding depression effect (Hinrichs et al., 2007).

303 Inclusion of metafounder in classical pedigree-based or single-step genetic evaluation
304 methods (PED_{MF} and H_{MF}) allowed to capture “recent” inbreeding that causes inbreeding
305 depression in motility.

306

307 Several studies indicate that inbreeding depression causes a reduction in semen quality traits
308 (Gage et al., 2006; Fitzpatrick and Evans, 2009; Maximini et al., 2011; Ferenčaković et al.,
309 2017). Sperm quality seems to be susceptible to inbreeding depression due to the dependence
310 of the spermatogenesis on the highly regulated developmental genes and to the appearance of
311 deleterious alleles or loss in heterozygosity (Gage et al., 2006; Fitzpatrick and Evans, 2009).
312 Recently, Dorado et al. (2017) indicated that high inbreeding had a moderate effect on semen
313 quality with an increased level of non-progressive spermatozoa despite of its high activity.

314

315

CONCLUSIONS

316 No inbreeding depression was detected for sperm volume and sperm concentration. Motility
317 of spermatozoa was unfavorably impacted by increasing of inbreeding in Basco-Béarnaise
318 breed. Inbreeding occurred in recent generations has an impact on inbreeding depression.
319 However, the effect of old inbreeding on motility was null, evidencing the existence of
320 purging by selection of deleterious recessive alleles affecting motility. A 10% increase in
321 inbreeding would result in reduction in the mean motility of 0.1 points in the score (from 0 to
322 5). The small decline in semen quality does not imply a negative economic impact for
323 breeders.

324

325 Runs of homozygosity allowed to estimate accurately inbreeding depression and to detect
326 “recent” inbreeding. However, it is restricted to use only genotyped animals. Metafounders is
327 an interesting method to estimate inbreeding depression due to “recent” inbreeding in
328 incomplete pedigrees including genotyped and ungenotyped animals.

329

330

331

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437 **Table 1.** Average, standard deviation (SD) and range of the evaluated semen traits.

Trait	Mean	SD	Range
Volume (mL)	1.41	0.63	0.20 – 4.80
Concentration ($\times 10^6$ spermatozoa / mL)	3.23	0.64	1.60 – 5.50
Motility (score 0 to 5)	4.61	0.54	0.00 – 4.98

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440 **Table 2.** Average inbreeding, standard deviations (SD) and range of the evaluated
441 coefficients.

Inbreeding coefficient	Method ¹	Mean	SD	Range
Marker-based (n ² = 533)	F_{SNP}	0.6111	0.0099	0.5864 – 0.6519
	$F_{ROH_{Total}}$	0.0468	0.0235	0.0020 – 0.1444
	$F_{ROH_{Old}}$	0.0337	0.0160	0.0020 – 0.0895
	$F_{ROH_{Recent}}$	0.0132	0.0144	0.0000 – 0.0884
Pedigree-based (n ² = 533)	F_{PED}	0.0388	0.0174	0.0000 – 0.1031
	$F_{PED_{non-zero}}$	0.0432	0.0162	0.0031 – 0.1066
	$F_{PED_{MF}}$	0.2287	0.0155	0.1862 – 0.2783
	$F_{H_{MF}}$	0.2226	0.0193	0.1747 – 0.3017

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443 ¹ Inbreeding coefficients: F_{SNP} = based on the proportion of homozygous SNP, $F_{ROH_{Total}}$ = based on runs of
444 homozygosity (ROH) with a minimum length of 4 Mb, $F_{ROH_{Old}}$ = ROH between 4 and 17Mb, $F_{ROH_{Recent}}$ =
445 ROH with a minimum length of 17 Mb, F_{PED} = pedigree-based inbreeding, $F_{PED_{non-zero}}$ = pedigree-based
446 inbreeding but accounting for non-zero relationships for unknown parents, $F_{PED_{MF}}$ = used the metafounder
447 relationships in pedigree-based inbreeding, and $F_{H_{MF}}$ = inbreeding is calculated from a combined relationship
448 matrix using pedigree and genotypes with metafounder relationships. ² n = number of rams.

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452 **Table 3.** Inbreeding depression and standard error (in parenthesis) for semen traits using
 453 different models.

Models ²	Semen traits ¹		
	Volume	Concentration	Motility
SNP	-0.901 (1.419)	-0.752 (1.589)	-2.230 (0.954)
ROH _{Total}	-0.931 (0.609)	-0.247 (0.684)	-0.905 (0.413)
ROH _{Old}	-1.187 (0.922)	0.582 (1.035)	-0.550 (0.626)
ROH _{Recent}	-0.967 (0.932)	-1.192 (1.049)	-1.539 (0.633)
PED	-0.096 (0.880)	1.104 (0.978)	-1.241 (0.681)
PED _{non-zero}	-0.290 (0.996)	1.056 (1.108)	-1.259 (0.771)
PED _{MF}	-0.979 (1.006)	1.617 (1.103)	-1.676 (0.768)
H _{MF}	-0.248 (0.703)	0.545 (0.807)	-1.115 (0.557)

454

455 ¹Values are expressed as the change in phenotypic mean per 100% increase in inbreeding. The models SNP,
 456 ROH_{Total}, ROH_{Old}, ROH_{Recent}, PED, PED_{non-zero}, PED_{MF} and H_{MF}, were defined according to the inbreeding
 457 coefficients used: F_{SNP} = based on the proportion of homozygous SNP, $F_{ROH_{Total}}$ = based on runs of
 458 homozygosity (ROH) with a minimum length of 4 Mb, $F_{ROH_{Old}}$ = ROH between 4 and 17Mb, $F_{ROH_{Recent}}$ =
 459 ROH with a minimum length of 17 Mb, F_{PED} = pedigree-based inbreeding, $F_{PED_{non-zero}}$ = pedigree-based
 460 inbreeding but accounting for non-zero relationships for unknown parents, $F_{PED_{MF}}$ = used the metafounder
 461 relationships in pedigree-based inbreeding, and $F_{H_{MF}}$ = inbreeding is calculated from a combined relationship
 462 matrix using pedigree and genotypes with metafounder relationships, respectively.

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467 **Figure 1.** Distribution of total and genotyped rams in the dataset across birth years.

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470 **Figure 2.** Correlations between different inbreeding coefficients.

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